

Ovarian agenesis and Mullerian duct dysgenesis in a karyotypically normal (46, XX) pre-pubertal girl with aberrant cognition: A case report and literature review

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Phenotypically normal pre-pubertal girl presenting with only a little delay in the onset of puberty and emotional lability is seldom thought to be suffering from a severe underlying congenital disability at the outset. Amongst different congenital causes for such presentation, Mayer-Rokitansky-Küster-Hauser syndrome is scarcely reported so far. This condition usually manifests with primary amenorrhoea and infertility in phenotypically and karyotypically normal 46, XX females. In the atypical form of this syndrome, additional congenital malformations involving mostly renal and skeletal systems are noticed along with Mullerian duct dysgenesis. **Case description:** A 12-year-old girl attended the adolescent clinic with complaints of generalised weakness, inadequate height gain and emotional lability. Initial clinical examination recorded genu valgus and absence of pubertal growth spurt. Subsequently, blood hormonal assay depicted hypergonadotropic hypogonadism state. Bilateral absence of gonads and Mullerian duct anomalies were detected further in an otherwise normal female karyotype (46, XX). No additional structural anomaly noticed. Developmental quotient assessment suggested intellectual disability. **Conclusions:** A stepwise approach incidentally revealed a rare condition like an atypical form of MRKH syndrome where bilateral gonadal agenesis and Mullerian duct dysgenesis were present but without any additional congenital malformations. Assessment of cognitive function in such cases should be sought for. Early detection of such rare case helps in building the emotional support of the family members in advance, long before the time when the patient might eventually present with primary amenorrhoea or infertility.

KEYWORDS 46, XX karyotype; Anomalies; Congenital disability; Gonadal agenesis; Intellectual disability; Mentally retarded; Paramesonephric derivatives

Introduction

Delayed onset of puberty in a normal female phenotype is a fairly known presentation of different underlying diseases which

might be congenital or acquired. Such clinical manifestation is usually associated with anatomic maldevelopment of genital structures or altered hormonal interplay due to dysfunction of hypothalamus, pituitary gland or gonads [1,2].

Mayer-Rokitansky-Küster-Hauser syndrome is one of the causes which might present early in life with delay in the appearance of secondary sexual characteristics where the patient appears normal female both phenotypically and karyotypically. However, it is evident that coexistence of gonadal agenesis with dysgenesis of paramesonephric duct (PMND) derivatives as a manifestation of an atypical form of Mayer-Rokitansky-Küster-Hauser syndrome is scarcely reported [3]. A similar case was evaluated incidentally for little delay in onset of pubertal growth

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spurt and ill-developed secondary sexual characters. Different clinical perspectives of this condition are being discussed here.

Case Report

A 12-year-old girl, accompanied by her parents, attended the adolescent clinic of the Department of Paediatrics at our institution with complaints of generalized weakness for several months and inadequate height gain. On further elaboration, poor school performance and emotional lability presented with the illness. No difficulties in performing daily routine work were reported. While eliciting clinical history, normal antenatal and perinatal events were recorded, but a delay in the achievement of different developmental milestones was noted based on the memory recall of the guardian. Birth records showed that she was a term baby and weighed 2.4 kilograms at birth. No major past illness was reported. The girl had a younger male sibling who was doing well, and other family history was found insignificant.

A general examination revealed a thin prepubertal girl with a height of 137 cm (below the 5th percentile for age as per the CDC growth chart for girls), weight of 33.5 kilograms (just above the 10th percentile for age as per the CDC growth chart for girls), body mass index of 17.8 (46th percentile for age as per the CDC BMI calculator for girls), and upper and lower body segment ratio of 1.02, and she followed commands well. Mid-parental height was found to be 159.5 cm. Genu valgus (distance between the medial malleoli was 4.8 cm in standing posture with the medial aspect of the knees touching each other) was noted, which was gradually increasing with age according to the parents. All vital signs were documented within the normal range for age and sex. No signs of nutritional deficiency were noticed. Physical examination revealed prepubertal breast development and nonappearance of axillary and pubic hair growth depicting Tanner Stage I female sexual maturity rating. External genitalia examination ruled out any ambiguity. Upon meticulous systemic examination, all other findings were documented as normal.

Initial blood work-up comprising a complete haemogram was found normal, with a blood haemoglobin level of 11.8 g/dl, and other measurements were found to be falling in the appropriate range for age, sex and ethnicity. Thyroid profile showed normal levels of tri-iodothyronine (T3), 1.39 ng/ml; tetra-iodothyronine (T4), 9.19 µg/dl; and thyroid-stimulating hormone, 1.25 µIU/ml. Plain roentgenographic evaluation of bilateral wrists and knees, which was done in conjunction with the evaluation of the widened wrist joints and genu valgus found on physical examination, unveiled no gross abnormalities except moderate rarefaction of bone matrices. The plain roentgenographic lateral view of both knees is shown in Figure 1. Serum vitamin D3 (25 hydroxy) level and total serum calcium level were 18.9 ng/ml and 9.5 mg/dl, respectively. On assessing the wrist and hand, bone age was estimated to be 9.3 years by the Greulich-Pyle (GP) method.

After few initial hospital visits, delayed pubertal growth spurt and insignificant development of female secondary sexual characteristics in the case led to investigate further for following hormonal assays which revealed lower values of serum oestradiol (E2) <5 pg/ml and 17-OH progesterone <0.5 ng/ml and higher values of luteinizing hormone (LH) 29.97 mIU/ml and follicular stimulating hormone (FSH) 56.4 mIU/ml. In the scenario of suspected hypothalamic-pituitary-gonadal (HPG) axis abnormality, normal serum prolactin and growth hormone (GH) level of 10.1 ng/ml and 0.135 ng/ml were found respectively which

Figure 1. Plain roentgenographic film (lateral view) of both the knees depicting moderate rarefaction of bone matrices.

Figure 2. Karyotype report of the patient under discussion.

Table 1 Comparison of the present case with other cases reported so far with bilateral gonadal absence and developmental anomalies of PMND derivatives in a normal female karyotype (46, XX).

<i>Cases reports by different authors</i>	<i>Age at diagnosis</i>	<i>External genitalia, Secondary sexual characteristics</i>	<i>Internal genitalia and gonads</i>	<i>Associated congenital structural anomaly</i>	<i>Cognition</i>
<i>Levinson et al. [6]</i>	17 years	Absence of vagina Absent secondary sexual character	Complete absence of internal genitalia, *b/l ovarian agenesis	Left sided double ureter	Not defined
<i>Medina et al. [11]</i>	Patient A: 20 years Patient B: 24 years (Unrelated)	Pre-pubertal Absent secondary sexual character	Rudimentary PMND derivatives but all component present, *b/l ovarian agenesis	None	Not defined
<i>Al-Awadi et al. (Patient no. 1) [12]</i>	18 years	Normal Poorly developed axillary and pubic hair, Tanner stage 2 of breast development	Uterus suggested by presence of small wedge of tissue in the mid-pelvic region, absent b/l fallopian tubes, *b/l ovarian agenesis	None	Not defined
<i>Chan et al. [13]</i>	17 years	Pre-pubertal Poorly developed secondary sexual character	Hypoplastic uterus with absence of *b/l fallopian tubes, *b/l ovarian agenesis	None	Not defined
<i>Gorgojo et al. [14]</i>	17 years	Pre-pubertal Presence of axillary and pubic hair, no breast development	Complete absence of internal genitalia, *b/l ovarian agenesis	Single pelvic kidney with multiple musculoskeletal defects	Apparently normal
<i>Megarbane et al. [15]</i>	17 years (Patient no. 1) 16 years (patient no. 2)	Normal Absent secondary sexual character	Hypoplastic uterus with absence of *b/l fallopian tubes, *b/l ovarian agenesis	Malformed fifth lumbar vertebrae in patient no.2	Normal
<i>Plevraki et al. (Patient no. 6) [16]</i>	•	Pre-pubertal Poorly developed secondary sexual character	Complete absence of internal genitalia, *b/l ovarian agenesis	Multiple skeletal deformities like bifid first sacral vertebrae, lumbar scoliosis etc.	Not defined
<i>Mutchinick et al. [3]</i>	17.5 years	Pre-pubertal Absent secondary sexual character	Rudimentary PMND derivatives but all component present, *b/l ovarian agenesis	Atrial septal defect (ASD)	Apparently normal
<i>Dede et al. [17]</i>	18 years	Pre-pubertal Absent secondary sexual character	Rudimentary uterus with normal fallopian tubes, *b/l ovarian agenesis	None	Not defined
<i>Tatar et al. [18]</i>	34 years (Patient no. 1) 23 years (Patient no. 2)	Normal Tanner stage 2 of axillary hair, sparse pubic hair, Tanner stage 1 of breast development	Complete absence of internal genitalia, *b/l ovarian agenesis	Triphalangeal thumbs and clinodactyly of the 5th fingers (in patient no. 2)	Mild and borderline mental retardation for Patient no. 1 and 2 respectively
<i>Bousfiha et al. [19]</i>	19 years	Pre-pubertal Tanner stage 2 of axillary and pubic hair, Tanner stage 3 of breast development	Complete absence of internal genitalia, *b/l ovarian agenesis	None	Not defined
<i>Kebaili et al. [1]</i>	21 years	Normal Tanner stage 2 of axillary and pubic hair, Tanner stage 1 of breast development	Complete absence of internal genitalia, *b/l ovarian agenesis	None	Not defined
<i>Miolo et al. [20]</i>	16 years (Dizygotic twins)	Pre-pubertal Presence of axillary and pubic hair, no breast development	Rudimentary PMND derivatives but all component present, *b/l ovarian agenesis	None	Not defined

<i>Manne et al. [21]</i>	20 years	Pre-pubertal Tanner stage 1 of secondary sexual characters with no breast development	Complete absence of internal genitalia, *b/l ovarian agenesis	Single horse shoe shaped kidney, bicuspid aortic valve with dilatation of aorta, fusion of first two lumbar vertebrae, short fourth metatarsal of left foot	Normal
<i>Al-Obaidi et al. [22]</i>	25 years (patient no.1) 16 years (patient no. 3)	Pre-pubertal Absent axillary and pubic hairs with Tanner stage 1 of breast development	Hypoplastic uterus with absence of *b/l fallopian tubes, *b/l ovarian agenesis	None	Not done
<i>Present case</i>	12 years	Pre-pubertal Tanner stage 1 of secondary sexual characters with no breast development	Hypoplastic PMND derivatives, *b/l ovarian agenesis	None	Mild intellectual disability

left the impression of normally functioning pituitary gland. The serum testosterone level was <0.13 ng/ml, while the serum dehydroepiandrosterone (DHEA) level was 1.57 ng/ml which depicted well-functioning adrenal glands.

To evaluate the hypergonadotropic-hypogonadal state, which could be either due to a functional abnormality or structural (anatomic) anomaly of the gonads, ultrasound of the pelvic region was done. Transvaginal ultrasound reported non-visualization of bilateral ovaries and uterus was not identified. The whole abdomen and inguinal region were searched with ultrasound for the ectopic location of the gonads. Afterwards, magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) which is the imaging tool of choice because of its high accuracy and excellent delineation of uterovaginal and ovarian anatomy, was advised to look for internal genitalia and gonads [4]. Findings of the MRI of whole abdomen and pelvis which corroborated with the ultrasound report, also recorded the absence of intra-abdominal gonads and uterus was not directly visualised instead a strip of tissue noticed to be lying between rectum and bladder, which suggested hypoplastic uterus. But no endometrial tissue was documented. Fallopian tubes could not be visualised. Every other intra-abdominal organ system was found to be normal without any structural defect. Vaginoscopy done in this case revealed a vaginal length of 4.5 cm ending in a cul-de-sac. MRI brain was normal. No other congenital anomaly was detected involving other organs of the body. Cytogenetic analysis of this phenotypically prepubertal female unveiled normal female karyotype 46, XX (using Giemsa banding) with no gross structural or numerical chromosomal anomaly or mosaicism. Karyotype report of the patient is shown in Figure 2.

For evaluation of cognitive function, she was advised to consult with a clinical psychologist later. On the assessment of the patient's development quotient (DQ) using the developmental screening test (DST), the DQ was found to be 52 with a mild level of mental retardation, and the intelligence quotient (IQ) inferred from the DQ was also 52 with 50% intellectual disability.

Discussion

The persistent characteristics of sexual infantilism were implicated to the hypergonadotropic hypogonadal state in the female discussed here, as evidenced by subsequent investigations. Later, bilateral absence of gonads was found out to be the reason behind the hypogonadal state. Now, bilateral gonadal absence and developmental defects of paramesonephric duct (PMND)

derivatives had invariably pointed towards a primary congenital disability for the case. Genu valgus noticed here, was interpreted to be acquired gradually due to poor bony matrix formation owing to the insufficiency of steroidal hormones, which was inferred from estimated delayed bone age. The manifestation of emotional instability and cognitive impairment could be corroborated to the hypogonadal state in this case, besides genetic predispositions [5].

Historically, gonadal agenesis syndromes were described as having an XY chromosomal component. A meticulous literature search revealed that only a few cases were reported describing bilateral ovarian agenesis with developmental defects of PMND derivatives in a karyotypically normal female (46, XX). Supposedly, the first case reported of its' kind was by Levinson et al. in 1976 where the atypical form of Mayer-Rokitansky-Küster-Hauser (MRKH) syndrome was described in a case who had bilateral gonadal absence with dysgenesis of PMND derivatives and left-sided double ureter [6]. MRKH syndrome is classically characterised by congenital absence of PMND derivatives in phenotypically normal 46, XX females. It is divided into two subtypes. In Type 1 or typical form of MRKH syndrome, structures develop from the caudal part of Mullerian duct-like the upper part of the vagina, cervix; the uterus is affected without any associated malformations. Normal anatomic and functional status of gonads is preserved here. Type 2 or atypical form of MRKH syndrome is described to be associated with additional congenital malformations usually involving renal and skeletal systems along with developmental anomaly of PMND derivatives. On a few rare occasions' ovarian dysgeneses in the form of streak gonads were also described with the atypical form. A distinct subset called MURCS (Mullerian duct aplasia, unilateral renal agenesis, and cervicothoracic somite anomalies) is often categorised under the atypical form of MRKH syndrome which is characterised by cervicothoracic defects [4,7] as a variation of an atypical form of MRKH syndrome, hyperandrogenism and chromosomal aberrations were reported in some cases [8-10]. In the context of the atypical form of MRKH syndrome, the present case had developmental defects involving PMND derivatives, but she didn't have any additional congenital malformations.

In contrast to gonadal dysgenesis or dysfunction, which could be found in the atypical form of MRKH syndrome, here both the ovaries were absent. No evidence of hyperandrogenism was noted, and no numerical aberration or mosaicism of chromosomes was seen on cytogenetic analysis. Thus, it is evident

that the present case had few distinct dissimilarities with conventional atypical form of MRKH syndrome, and additionally, intellectual disability was also noticed in this case.

So far, only a few cases had been reported of sexual infantilism due to the rare association of bilateral ovarian agenesis with developmental anomalies of PMND derivatives in a karyotypically normal female (46, XX). Various clinical aspects of these cases are compared with the present case in Table 1. Apart from these, a few cases are also reported with gonadal agenesis and developmental defects of PMND derivatives in phenotypically normal prepubertal females, but these cases reported distinct numerical chromosomal aberration and mosaicism on karyotyping instead of a normal 46, XX female karyotype [10,23]. Some cases have been reported with familial gonadal agenesis in siblings with female genotype and phenotype, but these cases had multiple associated congenital anomalies involving other systems [24,25]. Most of the patients died long before reaching puberty, and an autosomal recessive pattern of inheritance for the culprit gene was proposed. Rare foetal death with such congenital anomalies was also reported. However, no specific pattern of presentation or etiologic delineation had been described. Certain syndromes can mimic the clinical scenario of the present case, such as Turner syndrome, Swyer syndrome, Frasier syndrome, Androgen insensitivity syndrome, and Kennerknecht Vogel syndrome. These are important differentials, but the major discriminating factor is that they have karyotypes other than the 46, XX of normal females. It would not be an understatement if we recognized the present case as a female counterpart of the spectrum describing XY gonadal agenesis syndrome and group it under pure XX gonadal dysgenesis.

Conventionally gonadal agenesis can be noted to have XY association in most of the reported cases, while bilateral gonadal agenesis in karyotypically normal 46, XX female had been reported scarcely in conjunction with atypical form of MRKH syndrome. Kdous et al. reported a case of gonadal agenesis with MRKH syndrome, but further analysis is needed to determine whether this association was a form of manifestation of MRKH syndrome or it was different clinical entity itself [26]. The drawback of the present case report is that fluorescence in situ hybridization (FISH) analysis or CGH array could not be done due to the unavailability of resources. However, scarcely reported cases, like the present one, need larger datasets to determine the etiologic basis for the condition. The occurrence of MRKH syndrome is mainly sporadic, yet familial cases had also been reported on several occasions. But a clear pattern of inheritance has not been identified due to heterogeneous aetiology and incomplete penetrance. Presence of confounding variables, lack of clinical information and unavailability of molecular level evaluation of patient's relatives in such cases posed a hindrance in this perspective. Several chromosomal imbalances and rearrangements involving different chromosomal segments (like 1q21,16p11,17q12, 22q11 and Xp22, etc.) due to duplication and deletion were associated with MRKH syndrome [27]. Duplication of SHOX gene (Xp22) is one of such example which is known to be associated with familial inheritance of MRKH syndrome. Alongside different gene mutations involving LHX1, HNF1B, TBX6, ITIH5, WNT4, WNT7A, WNT9B genes are also implicated in this syndrome [28]. Although the pathogenetic contribution of these chromosomal or genetic aberrations in this syndrome is not clear so far, a mutation in the WNT4 gene had been seen to be found in a few MRKH patients with hyperandrogenism. Mutation in TBX6 and WNT7 genes are found

to be associated with congenital skeletal anomalies and limb malformations beside urogenital defect in MRKH patients. It is documented that a segment from the distal end of Xq13 to the distal end of Xq26 had been identified which is required to be present on both the X chromosomes in a female for the normal development of ovaries [10]. The however specific genetic predisposition for MRKH syndrome is not established yet. Mutations in the Müllerian-Inhibiting Factor (MIF) gene, or in the genes encoding Müllerian hormone (MH) or its receptor (MHR) were hypothesised to be involved in maldevelopment of PMND derivatives in the females, but its' association with MRKH syndrome is not proven yet [7,29].

Bilateral gonadal absence coexisting with dysgenesis of PMND derivatives in phenotypically and karyotypically normal 46, XX female is truly a rare finding and might be found in association with an atypical form of MRKH syndrome. Conventionally, the atypical form of MRKH syndrome is known to be associated with additional congenital malformations along with genital structure anomalies, involving renal and skeletal systems mostly although the present case under discussion had no additional congenital malformations except bilateral gonadal agenesis and dysgenesis of PMND derivatives. It is also crucial to evaluate the cognitive function in such cases, for detecting intellectual disability as evidenced by the present case. It is emotionally traumatic for the patient and her family to have such rare congenital disease what affects the productivity of life but early detection can help to build emotional support for them in advance and to institute appropriate supportive treatment in the form of hormone replacement therapy, cognitive behavioural therapy and vocational training at the earliest opportunity supposed to improve the quality of life [30].

Competing Interests

The authors declared that this review was done independently without any conflict of interest of any organizations that would lead this review to bias.

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Ethics approval and consent to participate

Obtained from our institutional ethical committee (Ref No. – IEC/NBMC/2018-19/88). Informed consent was obtained from the parents for anonymized information regarding medical records of their offspring to be published in this article.

List of Abbreviations

1. BMI – Body mass index
2. CDC - Centre for disease control
3. DHEA - Dehydroepiandrosterone
4. DQ- Developmental quotient
5. DST – Developmental screening test
6. FISH – Fluorescence in-situ hybridization
7. FSH – Follicular stimulating hormone
8. GH – Growth hormone

9. HPG axis – Hypothalamo-pituitary-gonadal axis
10. IQ – Intelligence quotient
11. LH – Luteinizing hormone
12. MRI - Magnetic resonance imaging
13. MRKH - Mayer-Rokitansky-Küster-Hauser
14. PMND – Para-mesonephric duct

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